

**PILOTS for robotic Inspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

Deliverable D6.1

General robot control station (first version)

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
CRC	Cyclic Redundancy Check
DDHL	Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer
DMS	Data Management System
DTO	Data Transfer Object
GPS	Global Positioning System
gRCS	Generic Robot Control Station
ID	Identifier
IP	Internet Protocol
I&M	Inspection and Maintenance
mRCS	Mission-specific Robot Control Station
NED	North-East-Down
RCS	Robot Control Station
WP	Work Package

Table 1. Acronym list.

Glossary of Terms

Term	Explanation
Asset data	Any data related to a physical asset, describing its characteristics and (spatial) features. This data will vary, depending on asset type. For example: manufacturer, material, year built, length, volume, operating temperature, 3D models, 2D drawings
Asset information	Used interchangeably with asset data
Inspection plan	A plan to perform inspections on an asset. Also known as Inspection Test Plan (ITP). The list of tasks is determined by the inspection strategy chosen (e.g. periodical, risk based, etc). An inspection plan may include a variety of inspection tasks. Not all of these inspection tasks may be performed by robotic solutions.
Inspection type	The inspection type indicates the technology/methodology used to perform an inspection task. Inspection types can be: Visual inspection, UT 4 point measurements, UT Grid measurements, CR, Dye Penetrant etc.
Inspection location	An asset can have Inspection Locations. Locations can be defined as early as the design phase of the asset (e.g. Corrosion Monitoring Locations (CML)). Other locations are a result of earlier inspection findings, defects or assessments or are created ad-hoc, during inspection. Typically, an Inspection location is being revisited periodically, to trend the defect development. This means, all findings/measurements need to be linked to an Inspection location.
Inspection tasks	An inspection task is the combination of an inspection type performed at and inspection location. This also includes cleaning/preparatory tasks.
Inspection equipment	The Inspection equipment consists of sensors and robotics system used to perform the inspection. Data includes sensor type, make, calibration etc.
Mission	The deployment of a robotic solution in the field to perform one or more inspection tasks. A mission requires mobilization/ demobilization of inspection equipment and personnel.
Mission plan	The full set of documents and data that is gathered/captured before, during and after a mission. See Table 37 in D3.1 for more details.
Mission definition	The inspection tasks from an inspection plan that are in scope of a mission.

Table 2. Glossary of terms.

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope of the document

As explained in D3.2 (PILOTING I&M platform design), the Robot Control Station is composed of a general and standardized part (gRCS) and a mission-specific one (mRCS). The main purpose of this document is to present the first version of the standardized control station software (gRCS) and its interfaces. This deliverable is the direct outcome of the work performed within task T6.1 (“General robot control station development”) during its first period.

1.2 Structure of the document

This document is organized as follows. Section 2 extends the definition of each module in the Generic Robot Control Station (gRCS) system, detailing its data inputs and outputs. In addition to explaining how communications between these modules are managed.

Section 3 presents the design and description of all the visual elements that make up the graphical user interface of the gRCS system.

Section 4 and section 5 define the communication interfaces with robotic systems and the Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer, respectively.

Finally, section 6 presents some conclusions and future work.

2. Software architecture

In deliverable D3.2 “PILOTING I&M platform design and validation metrics” a first approximation of the gRCS software architecture was obtained. In this first approach, the software modules that compose and carry out the functionalities provided in the gRCS were described.

On this occasion, more details of the content of this software architecture will be given (see Figure 1). On the one hand, all the sub-modules that are part of the gRCS software architecture will be identified and described. On the other hand, it will describe how communications are carried out between the different modules of the system.

Figure 1. Software architecture

2.1 Software modules

The definition of each module of the gRCS system is expanded below, detailing its data input and output interfaces.

DATA MODEL

Starting from the lowest part of the gRCS software architecture (see Figure 1), there is the layer corresponding to the data model. This layer oversees storing all the information of interest that is generated throughout the execution of the gRCS.

The data model is made up of a set of objects called DTO (Data Transfer Object). DTOs are simple objects that do not contain business logic but are only used to store and deliver information between modules in the system. One particularity of these DTOs is that they all inherit from a DTO interface, which simplifies the implementation of the communication interface between the modules of the system.

This layer is connected to the rest of the system through an interface that allows the upper layer to consult and modify the content of the data model.

CORE

In the central part of the software architecture, there is the layer corresponding to the core of the system. This module is mainly responsible for making decisions and managing the actions to be carried out on the rest of the modules of the system.

To do this, this layer is made up of a set of sub-modules called ACTION. Each ACTION is responsible for executing a single action on the system, such as adding a new waypoint to the planned path for the robotic system.

The execution of an ACTION consists of two phases: a first phase in which the desired action is carried out on the system and a second phase in which the higher layers are informed of the necessary updates. For example, the action in charge of adding a new waypoint to the planned path, first modifies the corresponding DTO in the data model and later informs the upper layers of the changes made.

An ACTION can also make requests on the communications layer, in addition to receiving information from the communication layer to later store this information in the data model.

In this layer there is another module called MANAGER. This module receives, from the upper layers, the requests to execute a specific action. And then it oversees selecting which ACTION it must execute to carry it out.

This layer is connected to the rest of the system through different communication interfaces. On the one hand, it is connected to the lower layer through an interface that allows consulting and modifying the content of the data model. On the other hand, it is connected to the upper

layer through an interface through which the executions of the actions are received and through which both information with the data model updates and requests about communications are sent.

COMMUNICATIONS

At the top of the software architecture is the communications layer. This layer is intended to manage all the necessary communications with subsystems external to the gRCS.

Apart from this, this layer is in charge of implementing the communication protocols defined for the different communication interfaces (see Sections 4 and 5).

As can be seen in Figure 1, this layer is made up of two main modules. The first one oversees implementing the communication protocol used to communicate with the gRCS and the robotic systems. The second is in charge of implementing the communication protocol used for the interface between the gRCS and the Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer.

Apart from managing the necessary communications with external subsystems and implementing the defined communication protocols, this layer provides an interface to the lower layer so that it can command the requests that need to be made on the external subsystems.

In addition, this layer connects with the lower layer through an interface that allows it to execute actions on the gRCS system. In this way, this layer can act on the data model updating it with the new information received through the communication interfaces with the external subsystems.

VIEW

Finally, at the top of the software architecture we also have the view layer. The main objective of this layer is to provide the gRCS user with a visualization and control interface of the running mission.

As can be seen in Section 3, through a set of elements such as colour indicators, text messages, maps and markers, this layer shows the user a visualization of the mission status. In addition, through controls such as buttons, boxes with editable values or mobile markers on the map, this module offers the user to control certain aspects of the mission in progress.

Mainly, this layer is made up of two modules. On the one hand, the main window where all the elements of the visualization interface are shown. And, on the other hand, the 3D map, where the user can manage the mission in progress through a three-dimensional viewer.

This layer connects to the lower layer through an interface that allows it to execute actions in the gRCS system. In this way, this layer can act on the data model updating it with the new information entered by the gRCS user.

In addition, this layer provides an interface to the lower layer through which it can be informed with the updates made on the data model.

2.2 Communications between modules

This section tries to explain in detail how communications between the different modules of the gRCS system are managed.

As previously mentioned, the data model is made up of a set of simple objects called DTOs, which allow to simplify the implementation of the communication interface between the different modules of the system.

Apart from this, to implement this communication interface, the signals and slots paradigm is used. This mechanism is a distinctive feature of the Qt framework, hence the gRCS system has been developed using this framework as the basis.

On the one hand, a signal can be seen as a notification that is emitted to the rest of the system by a specific module, and which could be of interest to be received by any other module. On the other hand, a slot is a function that would be contained within a module and that it would be interesting to execute when a specific signal is received from any other module.

The signals and slots paradigm have the following characteristics.

- A signal can send parameters.
- A slot can receive parameters.
- One signal can be connected to multiple slots.
- Multiple signals can be connected to the same slot.

Figure 2. Example of the signals and slots paradigm

Taking these characteristics into account and making use of the DTOs defined in the data model, it is possible to simplify the communication interface between the gRCS system modules, requiring very few signals and slots to be defined in the different modules.

It should be noted that for a signal to be attached to a specific slot, it is necessary to make a connection of both (see Figure 2). This is done in the gRCS system during the boot process, leaving all the modules in the system interconnected as shown in Figure 1.

Both the VIEW and the COMMUNICATIONS modules have defined a signal that they emit when they want to execute a specific action on the system. These signals are connected to a slot defined in the CORE module, which is responsible for executing these actions.

Furthermore, the CORE module has defined a signal that is emitted every time it wants to inform the rest of the system that some information in the data model has been modified. This signal is connected to a slot defined in the VIEW module, which is responsible for updating its components.

Finally, the CORE module has defined a signal that is emitted when it wants to make requests on the COMMUNICATIONS module. This signal is connected to a slot defined in the COMMUNICATIONS module, which is in charge of managing the received requests.

3. Design of the graphical user interface

This section will describe the graphical user interface of the gRCS and its functionalities. The gRCS will oversee monitoring the status and information of the robotic systems in PILOTING. For this purpose, there will be a series of panels where the information received will be displayed in different ways. In addition, it will also be possible to command different tasks to the robotic system and design the missions. It is decoupled from the overall application allowing it to be easily interchangeable with new graphical interfaces.

The design of any graphical interface must be based on a few features in order to be functional. These characteristics can be summarized as follows:

- Ease of understanding, learning and use.
- Intuitive design using windows, buttons, icons, etc.
- Use of suitable colours for key areas.
- Define a single object of use and design the interface with respect to it.

All these features have been considered for the development of the gRCS in order to minimize the need for specialization of the inspection operators.

The following sections will describe the functionalities that gRCS can solve, considering the normal operating flow.

Firstly, the connection and download with the DDHL server will be discussed. After that, the data obtained from the DDHL, such as 3D asset, exclusion and safety areas and a set of inspection tasks, will be displayed in the 3D viewer.

After this, each inspection task can be selected using a specific widget and its necessary information can be obtained. When an inspection task is selected, the 3D viewer will be highlighted.

Using the local path planning feature, the path of each mission can be defined over a set of inspection tasks using a 3D view of the environment and a set of tools such as adding waypoints by double-clicking or adjusting their position.

In addition, a series of windows will display all the information coming from the robotic system such as alarms, pose, speeds, etc. There will also be a console where all the relevant information of the execution is sent.

The following figure shows an overview of the gRCS graphical interface.

Figure 3. Overview of the gRCS graphical interface

3.1 Robot Messages management

To monitor everything that happens in the gRCS, a console is used to record all the events that provide useful information for the user. In this way, the operator will know clearly and intuitively what important events are occurring in the system. To indicate different types of events different colours are used (see Figure 4):

- **Information message:** This type of message informs the user that some event has occurred. This message is displayed in white.
- **Warning message:** This type of message informs the user that some unexpected event has occurred. This message is displayed in yellow.
- **Error message:** This type of message informs the user that some error event has occurred. This message is displayed in red.

Figure 4. Example of console message types

It is important to note that the events displayed on the console are related to both, the events that occur due to the user interaction with the gRCS and to the events that are received by the robot's communication protocol. Moreover, all these events are not only displayed in the console, but these events are also saved to a file as part of the mission execution results.

3.2 Connection with DDHL

As defined in previous documents, the DDHL, (Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer), which takes care of the collection of the mission data from the robotic systems, will assist communication between the Robots Control Stations (generic and specific) and the DMS (Data Management System).

In the gRCS graphical interface, there are a series of buttons in the following toolbar to perform basic operations on DDHL (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Toolbar buttons associated with DDHL

These buttons have the following functionalities:

- Configure DDHL Communications:** Clicking this button will display a configuration panel of the options for connecting to the DDHL as it is shown in Figure 6. In case an invalid IP address or a port out of a certain range is entered, a pop-up will appear, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6. DDHL configuration dialog

Figure 7. Invalid DDHL configuration field dialog

- **Download data from DDHL:** When this button is pressed, the connection data to the server will be confirmed, as shown in Figure 8. In addition, the identifier of the inspection plan to be downloaded from the DDHL must be selected.

Figure 8. DDHL download data confirmation dialog

When the "OK" button is clicked, the gRCS will connect to the server and, if the connection fails, the error message shown in the next figure will be displayed.

Figure 9. Download data from DDHL failed window

After that, it will start downloading all the data associated with the selected inspection plan. As the download may take some time, a progress window (see Figure 10) will appear while downloading.

Figure 10. Downloading data from DDHL progress bar

In case the downloaded data is corrupted or invalid, the error message shown in Figure 11 will be displayed.

Figure 11. Corrupted downloaded data from DDHL window

When the process has been correctly completed, and the downloaded data is valid, a pop-up (see Figure 12) will be displayed in order to inform the operator that the download has been successful. Moreover, a console message as seen in Figure 13 is displayed to log this event.

Figure 12. Successfully downloaded data from DDHL window

Figure 13. Successfully downloaded data from DDHL console message

- Upload data to DDHL:** When the mission is completed, all logs and data related to the mission should be uploaded to the DDHL. As soon as this button is clicked, the DDHL upload manager will be displayed. This interface is shown in Figure 14. As it can be seen, the information associated with a mission can be quickly analyzed. In addition, a count of the number of mission tasks associated with that mission will

be displayed. For each one of them, the operator will have a button to get the information of the associated mission task. When this button is pressed window will appear with all the information associated with that mission task. This window is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 14. Upload mission data to DDHL manager

Figure 15. Information associated with selected Mission Task

Using this manager, the user can choose which missions to upload to the DDHL server and see all the information associated with them. In addition, it should be noted that this process can be carried out offline, i.e. after the inspection has been completed. This will avoid unnecessary waiting in the area where the inspection has been performed and it will be possible to make sure that you have a stable and fast internet connection.

By clicking on the check button, the missions to be uploaded will be selected. As shown in Figure 14, the upload waiting time increases with the number of selected missions. After selecting the missions to be uploaded, the pop-up window shown in Figure 16 will appear as an upload confirmation.

Figure 16. Upload mission data to DDHL confirmation dialog

As the data transfer may take some time, a progress window will appear while the data is being uploaded. The number of missions successfully uploaded to the DDHL server will be displayed, as shown in the following figure.

Figure 17. Upload mission data to DDHL progress bar

If the uploading mission data to DDHL is completed successfully, a pop-up window and a message in the console will be displayed to inform the operator that the upload has been successful.

Figure 18. Successfully upload mission data to DDHL window

Figure 19. Successfully upload data to DDHL console message

3.3 Inspection plan management

When the desired inspection plan has been downloaded from the DDHL, the relevant elements will be displayed in the 3D visualizer. Figure 20 shows a preview of the general appearance of the 3D visualizer with an example asset contained in the inspection plan downloaded from the DDHL. Among the data downloaded from DDHL are exclusion zones, security zones and inspection tasks of different types.

Figure 20. Inspection plan items over 3D Visualizer

The asset data contains different items that are going to be discussed below. However, it is important to emphasize that the representation of these items is an aspect that must be

considered when making the gRCS intuitive, easy to use, and above all to make an accurate planning of the mission by the operator.

3.3.1 Asset 3D Model

The main element contained in the downloaded asset is the 3D model obtained from the location where the mission is to be carried out. The 3D model of the area to be inspected shall be received in the form of a point cloud. The following figure shows an example of this point cloud.

Figure 21. Generated point cloud representation

3.3.2 Exclusion areas

The exclusion areas are the zones of the map restricted for the operation of the robotic system. The reason for the exclusion areas lies in robotic vehicles, it is important that during the mission execution, the robotic vehicles cannot operate in these zones.

For example, in the case of viaducts, these zones will correspond to areas where vehicles cannot pass through or pillars that should not be inspected. These areas are displayed in translucent red, each one has its own name and its own shape and size.

Figure 22. Exclusion areas representation

3.3.3 Safety areas

The definition of these zones is necessary because generally the locations where inspections are to be carried out will have areas that may present a risk to the operators. Therefore, these areas will indicate the location where operators will have a safe working area.

In addition, this is where the robotic vehicle should be located at the start of the mission and, in the case of the aerial robotic vehicle, the take-off and landing location. These zones are shown on the display in solid green, as can be seen in Figure 23.

Figure 23. Safety areas representation

3.3.4 Inspection task location

The last asset item displayed in the visualizer is the location where the inspection task is to be carried out. The inspection plan might contain more than one inspection task, i.e., at the same time might be displayed different inspection task location items in the 3D visualizer. There are several types of inspection task locations depending on its forms. As it can be seen in the next figure the “*inspection_task_1*” location is an area, the “*inspection_task_2*” and “*inspection_task_3*” locations are a point. The items that represent these location types are shown in translucent yellow.

Figure 24. Inspection tasks representation

Additionally, in order to manage the inspection tasks, the “*Inspection Plan Widget*” shown in Figure 25 has been created. The main purpose of this widget is to manage and to obtain information about the inspection plan and the tasks associated with it.

Figure 25. Inspection plan widget

The top button of the widget will display general information of the current inspection plan. The information is shown as in Figure 26 with the following fields.

Figure 26. Inspection plan information dialog

- **Name:** The name of the inspection plan.
- **ID:** The identifier of inspection plan.
- **Creation Date:** The creation date of the inspection plan.
- **Last Update Date:** The last update date of the inspection plan.
- **Description:** The description of the inspection plan.

As it is shown in Figure 25, a list of the different inspection tasks associated with the inspection plan is displayed. This list displays brief information of each inspection task as its name, identifier and information button , which is necessary to obtain more information about each inspection task. The inspection task information displayed by clicking in the information button is shown in the following image.

Figure 27. Inspection task information dialog

The information displayed by clicking in the inspection task information button has the following fields:

- **Name:** The inspection task name.
- **ID:** The inspection task identifier.
- **Creation Date:** The creation date of the inspection task.
- **Last Update Date:** The last update date of the inspection task.
- **Location Type:** The location type on the asset that needs to be inspected, i.e., if this location is an area, point or part.
- **Description:** The description of the inspection task.

Another relevant functionality has been implemented in order to facilitate the management of the inspection task. If the row of any of the inspection tasks in the inspection plan widget is clicked, the associated task will be highlighted in the 3D viewer. A concrete example seen in Figure 28 shows the “*inspection_task_1*” highlighted due to the inspection task 1 clicked in the inspection plan widget.

Figure 28. Inspection task highlighted over 3D view

3.4 Planned local path

In order to plan the inspection to be carried out by the robotic system and the path to be followed, as well as the performance of specific inspection tasks, there is an edition mode in the gRCS graphical interface that allows to create and modify paths. This mode can be seen in Figure 29 and it appears by clicking the “edition mode” button , which is located on the toolbar of the application.

The paths are composed of reference points along which the robotic system must navigate with a certain orientation, also known as waypoints. As can be seen, on the left side of the application there is a widget dedicated to waypoint edition. It should be noted that every waypoint has an associated inspection task.

Moreover, in order to carry out the mission, the robotic system must establish the relationship between the reference system of the asset 3D model and its own reference system in order to follow the inspection plan established by the inspector. In this context, it is necessary for the user to be able to visually indicate this relationship in the gRCS. For this purpose, the home is used, which indicates the initial position of the vehicle with respect to the reference system of the asset 3D model.

Figure 29. gRCS in local path planner mode

For path management, creating waypoints, editing the home point or editing the path, the buttons shown in Figure 30 of the toolbar will be used.

Figure 30. Path edition toolbar

- **Create Path:** Clicking this button, the user can add new local paths to the actual mission. This tool is only enabled when the gRCS is in edition mode.
- **Edit Path:** Clicking this button, the user can edit local paths in the mission task. This tool is only enabled when the gRCS is in edition mode and at least one local path exists.
- **Edit Home:** Clicking this button, the home position can be edited. It can be edited by clicking twice on the left button of the mouse in the visualizer or by clicking the right button over the home platform in the visualizer using the home parameters menu that appears by right-clicking to the home platform (see Figure 31).

Figure 31. Home representation

The home parameters shown in Figure 32 that can be editable are discussed below:

- **Position X:** It represents the home position in meters of the X axis.
- **Position Y:** It represents the home position in meters of the Y axis.
- **Position Z:** It represents the home position in meters of the Z axis.
- **Yaw Angle:** It represents the home yaw angle in degrees.

Figure 32. Home parameters menu

Depending on the type of robot used to perform the inspection, it is possible to choose between creating and editing the route in 2D or 3D mode. The 3D editing mode allows the placement of waypoints on the surfaces of the displayed point clouds. This is especially useful in the case of ground robots, as they operate on the surface of the inspection area, i.e. the viaduct.

As for the 2D editing mode, it will not be necessary to place waypoints on any surface. This is convenient in the case of aerial robots, as waypoints can be placed at any 3D position in space. It is therefore more convenient to place the waypoints in 2D and then modify the height of the waypoints if necessary.

The “Waypoints Editor Widget” seen in Figure 33 is used to achieve two functionalities. The first one is to display all the different waypoints in all the paths that have been created in the gRCS. It can be seen in the bottom part of the widget as a list of paths each one with its

waypoints. Each path has its own unique identifier. Moreover, each waypoint has its own sequence number that identifies it.

The screenshot shows a 'Waypoints Editor' window with the following fields and values:

- Identifier: 4
- Sequence: 4
- Task Id: 1
- Pos x (m): -4,43
- Pos y (m): 2,88
- Altitude (m): 2,50
- Yaw (°): 0,00

Below the fields is an 'Apply Changes' button. At the bottom is a table with the following data:

Route Id	SeqN	Task ID	PosX (m)	PosY (m)	Alt (m)	Yaw (°)
1	0	1	1.983	3.000	2.500	0.000
	1	1	2.050	-5.017	2.500	0.000
	2	1	-4.167	-4.533	2.500	0.000
	3	1	-4.433	2.883	2.500	0.000

Figure 33. Waypoint editor widget

The second functionality that this widget achieves is editing the waypoint parameters. By selecting each waypoint in this widget, the information of the waypoint in the upper part of the widget is updated with the selected waypoint parameters. The waypoint position in X axis, the waypoint position in Y axis, the waypoint altitude, the waypoint yaw angle or the associated inspection task can be edited by changing its value and pressing the “Apply Changes” button.

To conclude this section, a complete planned path is shown in Figure 34. There are three different inspection tasks, therefore, when the waypoint list is uploaded correctly to the robotic system, the mission will contain three mission tasks. It should be noted that two colours are currently used to represent waypoints; purple and blue. The blue colour represents a waypoint of transit. The violet colour also represents a waypoint and the start of a new mission task. From a purple waypoint until the next one that appears will be all the waypoints associated with the same inspection task.

Figure 34. Example of a complete planned path

3.5 Mission management

In order to deploy a robotic solution in the field to perform one or more inspection tasks, a mission must be defined. This mission will be defined on the planned path that has been uploaded to the robotic system.

To edit some aspects of the mission and to be able to visualize all the mission tasks together and obtain information from them, the widget shown in Figure 35 has been created. For this purpose, it contains a series of interactive buttons and a dynamic list of mission tasks.

Figure 35. Mission management widget

In the upper part of the widget, there is a button to edit this mission. Clicking this button prompts a dialog as seen in Figure 36. It presents different fields such as the name of the mission, the creation date and a description of the mission. Both the name and the description can be edited at any time.

Figure 36. Edit mission dialog

Each mission task will be associated with a set of waypoints, as defined above, and a target inspection task.

Therefore, as soon as the planned path is successfully uploaded to the robotic system, a new mission will be created, and the list of mission tasks shown in the widget in Figure 37 will be filled.

Moreover, it should be noted that with each new planned path uploaded to the robot, a new mission will be created. In the figure shown below, the status of the widget can be observed when a planned path has been successfully uploaded to the robotic system.

Figure 37. Mission widget with several mission tasks

The Mission management widget contains a list with the different mission tasks associated to the mission. This list displays brief information about each mission task such as its name, the inspection task associated to it, and an edit button , in case the operator to specify some mission task information. By clicking on this button, the following dialog will be displayed to the user to introduce the information related with the mission task.

The image shows a dialog box titled "Mission Task Information" with a close button (X) in the top right corner. The dialog contains the following fields:

- Creation Date:** 2021/05/28 14:33:20
- Last Update Date:** 2021/05/28 16:46:40
- Inspection Task Associated:** Name of Inspection Task 1
- Name:** Name of Mission Task 1 (text input field)
- Description:** A large text area containing the text: "In this field, the description of the mission task 1 will be added by the operator." with a cursor at the end of the line.

At the bottom right of the dialog, there are two buttons: "Cancel" (with an X icon) and "OK" (with a checkmark icon).

Figure 38. Mission task information dialog

- **Creation Date:** The mission task creation date.
- **Last update Date:** The last mission task update date.
- **Inspection Task Associated:** The inspection task associated with the mission task.
- **Name:** This field allows the user to change the name of the mission task in order to easily identify it.
- **Description:** This includes detailed descriptions and instructions about the execution of the mission task.

If the “Cancel” button is pressed the new mission task is not updated. However, if the “OK” button is pressed, the mission task with the introduced fields is updated.

3.6 Connection with Robotic System

In the same way as for the DDHL connection, the toolbar will have buttons dedicated to establishing the connection to the robotic system. In order to connect to the robotic system, it is necessary that a mission has been previously created. The following buttons will be used to configure the communication, connect and disconnect.

Figure 39. Connection bar

These buttons have the following functionalities:

- **Configure Communication Options with Robotic System:** Clicking this button will display a configuration dialog of the options for connecting to the robotic system. This dialog is shown in Figure 40.

Field	Value
Heartbeat Interval (ms)	1
Local System ID	2
Local Component ID	26
Local IP	127.0.0.1
Local Port	14540
Target System ID	1
Target IP	192.168.0.20
Target Port	14541

Figure 40. Communication options dialog

The different robotic system communication options that are editable in this window are discussed below:

- **Heartbeat Interval:** The interval of a periodic signal to indicate normal operation of the robotic system.
- **Local System ID:** The identifier of the local system.
- **Local Component ID:** The identifier of the local component.
- **Local IP:** The local IP address.
- **Local Port:** The port of the local system.
- **Target System ID:** The identifier of the target system.
- **Target IP:** The IP address of the target system.
- **Target Port:** The port of the target system.

When the “OK” button is clicked, all this data will be saved for later connection to the robotic system. If the format of any of the fields in the communication options is not valid, an error message will appear. An example of a formatting error in the field is shown in the next figure.

Figure 41. Format error window

- Connect to Robotic System:** When this button is clicked, the connection with the robotic system will be confirmed using the last communication options. This is shown in Figure 42.

Figure 42. Connection to robotic system confirmation

When the “Yes” button is clicked, the gRCS will try to connect to the server and, if the connection is successful, messages in the console will appear (see Figure 43).

Figure 43. Connection successfully message

If the gRCS cannot connect to the robotic system, an error message as shown in Figure 44 will appear. Moreover, a console message is displayed in order to log this event (see Figure 45).

Figure 44. Connection error window

Figure 45. Connection error console message

- **Disconnect from the Robotic System:** If the user presses this button, a pop-up to confirm the disconnection operation is displayed. This is shown in Figure 46.

Figure 46. Disconnection confirmation window

If the user confirms the disconnection operation pressing the “Yes” button, the gRCS closes and removes the communication socket with the robotic system. If this operation succeeds, a confirmation pop-up window is displayed as seen in the following figure.

Figure 47. Disconnection from the robotic system successful window

Moreover, a message appears in the console to log this event (see Figure 48). Alternatively, the user can cancel and end the disconnect operation by pressing the “No” button.

Figure 48. Disconnection from the robotic system successful message

3.7 Alarms management

To perform a series of actions on the robotic system, a widget with buttons has been designed. Along this and future subsections, the functionalities of these buttons will be explained. This window with the set of buttons is shown in Figure 49.

The gRCS must be capable of downloading the list of alarms defined in each robotic system when the connection has been established. For this reason, a “Download Alarm List” button has been created. This button is only enabled when there is an active connection with the robotic system, and there is a mission already created. It is shown in Figure 49.

Figure 49. Download alarm list button

When this button is pressed, the gRCS sends a request to the robotic system to obtain the alarm list. The gRCS waits until the download is completed and informs the user with a progress window. This window is shown in Figure 50.

Figure 50. Download alarm list progress window

If the gRCS does not receive a response, a pop-up window shown in Figure 51 and a warning message to the user as shown in Figure 52 are displayed.

Figure 51. Download alarm list timeout window

Figure 52. Download alarm list timeout message

When the gRCS receives a reply, it checks the format of the received alarm list and if the alarm list is invalid, an error window as shown in Figure 53 is displayed.

Figure 53. Alarm list format error window

If the alarm list is valid, a window is displayed in order to inform that the alarm list has been successfully downloaded (see Figure 54). Moreover, a console message appears to log this event.

Figure 54. Alarm list successfully downloaded window

Figure 55. Alarm list successfully download message

Besides, the alarm list is updated in the robot alarms widget. This widget is shown in Figure 56. It contains data related to the robot alarms. In the upper area there is an alarm that informs about the connection status with the robotic system, if the gRCS is connected to any robotic system the “COMMS STATUS” indicator appears in green and if it is not connected it appears in red.

Once the gRCS has received a valid alarm list, this widget displays the information related to it as the ID and name from each alarm. The description of each alarm is displayed by a tooltip when the mouse is hovering over each alarm name.

Figure 56. Robot alarm widget with alarm list

From now on, each alarm on the list is refreshed with its status. Moreover, each of the alarms is refreshed with the number of errors and warnings that have already occurred for that alarm. If the alarm is correct, the status will appear in green, if the alarm is in warning, the status will appear in yellow and if the alarm is in error it will appear in red (see Figure 57). If the status appears in grey, it means that the gRCS has not received any alarm status yet (see Figure 56).

Figure 57. Robot alarm widget with alarm list updating

3.8 High Level actions management

The gRCS must be capable of downloading the list of high-level actions defined in each robotic system. For this reason, a “Download High Level Actions” button has been created. This button is situated in the “Robot Control” widget and is only enabled when there is an active connection with the robotic system, as shown in the following figure.

Figure 58. Download high level action list button

When the “Download High Level Actions” button is pressed the gRCS sends a request to the robotic system to obtain the high-level action list. The gRCS waits until the download is completed and informs the user with a progress window. This window is shown in Figure 59.

Figure 59. Download high level action list progress window

If the gRCS does not receive a response, a pop-up window in Figure 60 and a warning message to the user as shown in Figure 61 are displayed.

Figure 60. Download high level action list timeout window

Figure 61. Download high level action list timeout message

When the gRCS receives a reply, it checks the format of the high-level action list and if the high-level action list is invalid, an error window as shown in Figure 62 is displayed.

Figure 62. Download high level actions format error

If the high-level action list is valid, a window is displayed in order to inform the user that the high-level actions have been downloaded successfully as shown in Figure 63. Moreover, a console message appears to log this event (see Figure 64).

Figure 63. High level actions successfully downloaded window

Figure 64. High level actions successfully downloaded console message

Additionally, the high-level action list is updated in the robot control widget. This widget is shown in Figure 65. This widget shows information related to the high-level actions such as each action name and its description (tooltip).

Figure 65. High level action list

The high-level action list buttons are only enabled when the gRCS is connected to any robotic system. When any of these buttons are pressed, a confirmation window will appear as shown in Figure 66.

Figure 66. High level action command confirmation window

If the user confirms the operation by pressing in the “Yes” button, the high-level action command request associated with the pressed button will be sent to the robotic system and the progress of this operation will be displayed as shown in the following figure.

Figure 67. Executing high level action command progress bar

Alternatively, the user can cancel the operation by pressing the “No” button. If there is any problem sending the high-level action command an error console message will appear (see Figure 68). However, if the command has been sent successfully to the robotic system a console message will be displayed (see Figure 69).

Figure 68. Send high level action command warning message

Figure 69. Send high level action command confirmation message

3.9 Checklist management

The gRCS must be capable of downloading the checklist defined in each robotic system when the connection with the robotic system has been established. For this reason, a “Download checklist” button has been created. This button is situated in “Robots Control” widget which will be discussed later. This button is only enabled when there is an active connection, and there is a mission already created. It is shown in Figure 70.

Figure 70. Download checklist button

When this button is pressed, the gRCS sends a request to the robotic system to obtain the checklist. The gRCS waits until the download is completed and informs the user with a progress window as shown in Figure 71.

Figure 71. Download checklist progress window

If the gRCS does not receive a response, a pop-up window in Figure 72 and a warning message to the user as shown in Figure 73 are displayed.

Figure 72. Download checklist timeout window

Figure 73. Download checklist timeout message

If the checklist is valid, a console message appears in order to inform the operator of this event as can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 74. Download checklist confirmation message

From this moment onwards, the robotic system checklist is stored in the gRCS, if the user wants to start the check operation is necessary to press the “checklist button” situated in the tool bar.

If the user presses this button when there is no previous checklist downloaded, an error window as shown in Figure 75 will be displayed. If there is a checklist stored in the gRCS, a dialog with the checklist will be displayed. The dialog (Figure 76) contains information about the name and the description of each check. Additionally, each check is associated with two checkboxes in order to let the user indicate if the check has been verified successfully (“OK” checkbox), if the check has not been verified successfully (“FAIL” checkbox) or if neither of these options have been carried out.

Figure 75. Show checklist error window

Figure 76. Show checklist dialog

If the user checks and completes the elements of this list one by one and confirms the operation by pressing the "OK" button the gRCS stores the checklist completed by the user. Alternatively, the user can cancel and end the check operation by pressing the “Cancel” button.

3.10 Loaded Waypoint List

In order to manage the mission in the robotic system, an “Upload Waypoint List”, “Download Waypoint List” and a “Set Current Waypoint Item” buttons have been created. These buttons are situated in the “Robots Control” widget (Figure 77) which manage the control actions that the gRCS can request from the robotic system. Some of these actions have been discussed previously. However, there are some of them related to the mission and are going to be discussed in this section.

Figure 77. Waypoint list management buttons

- **Upload Waypoint List:** This button is only enabled when there is an active connection, and when there is a mission already created. Moreover, it allows the user to request to the robotic system the uploading of the current waypoint list. This button is shown in Figure 78.

Figure 78. Upload waypoint list button

After pressing the “Upload Waypoint List” button, the confirmation message shown in Figure 79 will be displayed.

Figure 79. Upload waypoint list confirmation window

Due to communication latency, while sending the waypoint list to the robotic system, the progress window shown in Figure 80 will appear.

Figure 80. Upload waypoint list progress bar

In the case that the waypoint list upload fails, the window in Figure 81 will appear showing the reason for the failure. Moreover, a console message will be displayed in order to log this event. This is shown in Figure 82.

Figure 81. Upload waypoint list error window

Figure 82. Upload waypoint list error console message

If the upload is successful, a console message as seen in Figure 83 will be displayed.

Figure 83. Successful waypoint list upload console message

Once confirmation is obtained from the robotic system that the waypoint list has been successfully loaded, the colour of the path that has been loaded shall be changed to green. In Figure 84 is shown the uploaded waypoint list in green colour and a local waypoint list in yellow colour.

Figure 84. Local waypoint list and uploaded waypoint list

- **Download Waypoint List:** This button allows the user to download the waypoint list loaded in the robotic system. It is shown in Figure 85. This functionality is necessary in the gRCS because the robotic system might change the waypoint list during the mission. If that happens, the robotic system will inform the gRCS of this event.

Figure 85. Download waypoint list button

When the user is aware that the robotic system has changed its waypoint list, the user might press the “Download Waypoint List” button. If this button is pressed, a confirmation window as shown in Figure 86 will be displayed.

Figure 86. Download waypoint list confirmation window

Due to communication latency, while downloading the waypoint list from the robotic system, the progress window shown in Figure 87 will appear.

Figure 87. Download waypoint list progress bar

In the case that the waypoint list download fails, the window in Figure 88 will appear showing the reason for the failure. Moreover, a console message will be displayed in order to log this event. This is shown in Figure 89.

Figure 88. Download waypoint list error window

Figure 89. Download waypoint list error console message

If the download is successful, the waypoint list is updated with the new information.

- **Set Current Waypoint Item:** This button allows the user to set to the robotic system the current waypoint that is going to be carried out. The user can choose between the different waypoints available in the waypoint list in the gRCS. This button is shown in Figure 90.

Figure 90. Set current waypoint item button

When this button is pressed a confirmation window as shown in Figure 91 is displayed.

Figure 91. Set current waypoint item confirmation window

If the current waypoint item is successfully set, a console message is displayed in order to inform the user of this event. This is shown in Figure 92.

Figure 92. Successfully set current waypoint item console message

3.11 Robot Telemetry management

The gRCS must be capable of receiving and processing the pose information sent by the specific robot system. The gRCS expects to periodically receive messages with the pose of the robotic vehicle. In order to display all this information, the telemetry widget (Figure 93) has been created in the gRCS.

Telemetry	
Name	Value
▼ General Information	
Current Waypoint	-
Waypoint Type	-
Current Inspection Task	-
▼ Vehicle Position NED	
North (m)	2.20000
East (m)	1.10000
Down (m)	-3.30000
▼ Vehicle Velocity NED	
North (m/s)	4.40000
East (m/s)	5.50000
Down (m/s)	6.60000
▼ Vehicle Attitude	
Roll (rad)	0.00000
Pitch (rad)	0.00000
Yaw (rad)	3.14152
▼ Vehicle Angular Velocity	
Roll (rad/s)	0.20000
Pitch (rad/s)	0.20000
Yaw (rad/s)	0.00000

Figure 93. Telemetry Widget

The information displayed in the telemetry widget is related to the pose of the specific robotic vehicle. This information has the following fields:

- **Current Waypoint:** The index of the current waypoint.
- **Waypoint Type:** Information about the type of the current waypoint.
- **Current Inspection Task:** Information about the current inspection task.
- **Vehicle Position NED:** The position along north, east, and down direction in meters of the robotic vehicle.
- **Vehicle Velocity NED:** The velocity along north, east and down direction in meters per second of the robotic vehicle.
- **Vehicle Attitude:** The roll, pitch and yaw attitude in radians of the robotic vehicle.
- **Vehicle Angular Velocity:** The roll, pitch and yaw angular velocity in radians per second of the robotic vehicle.

When the gRCS receives a message with pose information of the robotic vehicle, it updates the map view displayed to the user with the received information (see Figure 94).

Figure 94. Pose and vehicle path displayed

If after a while the gRCS does not receive any message from the robotic system, the “COMMS STATUS” indicator in the robot alarm widget will be updated to red, indicating that the communications interface with the robotic system is not working correctly. This behavior can be seen in the following figure.

Figure 95. Alarms widget when connection is lost

4. Communications interface with robotic systems

This section defines the communication interface used for data transfer between the robotic systems and the general robot control station.

Because gRCS is used to monitor the status in real time of a running mission, this communications interface is required to have a permanently open and robust connection between the robotic system and the gRCS. Otherwise, there could be cases in which crucial information is lost during the execution of the mission.

The communication channel between the robotic system and the gRCS may not have a high bandwidth, so a communication protocol with a very simple and light header must be selected, maximizing the amount of useful data in each package. In addition, for the same reason, it is required that all the information sent through this communication channel to be serialized.

MAVLink is a protocol widely used in communication systems between drones and ground control stations. It is well suited for communication links with very limited bandwidth and is highly optimized for systems with limited resources. Furthermore, MAVLink verifies the integrity of the data during transmission using CRC-16/MCRF4XX checksum.

The MAVLink protocol is open source and can be easily adapted to the needs of each system without losing any of its benefits. This is what we have done in PILOTING, we have adapted this protocol by creating our own messages and defining our own message sequences, taking advantage of the basis of this communication protocol and the benefits it provides us.

This adaptation is carried out by defining the content of the new messages through a file in XML format, which is later used to generate the source code that will be used both in the gRCS and in robotic systems. It should be noted that MAVLink allows the generation of source code for the main programming languages used in robotics, such as: C, C++, C#, Java, Python, etc.

Through this procedure, MAVLink allows this communication interface to be flexible to changes and scalable, thus accepting to be expanded with new functionalities in an agile and simple way. To do this, the XML file has to be modified and then the source code must be generated, which will contain the new functionalities.

For all the above, MAVLink has been selected as the protocol for this communication interface. Taking advantage of the benefits already existing in its base and adapting its messages to the needs of PILOTING, and all this without implying any limitation for the future exploitation of the system.

4.1 Communication sequences

Next, the message exchange sequences between the robotic systems and the general robot control station are detailed.

4.1.1 Upload the waypoint list to the robotic system

Before starting a mission, the gRCS has to send the waypoint list to the robotic system.

The diagram below shows the communication sequence to upload a new waypoint list to the robotic system. This diagram assumes that all operations are performed successfully.

Figure 96. Upload the waypoint list to the robotic system

In more detail, the sequence of operations is:

1. The gRCS sends a WAYPOINT_LIST_COUNT message (see section 4.2.1.1) including the number of waypoint items to be uploaded (count).
 - a. A timeout must be started for the gRCS to wait on the WAYPOINT_LIST_READ (see section 4.2.1.2) response from the robotic system.
 - b. If the timeout expires without a response being received, then the WAYPOINT_LIST_COUNT message must be resent.

2. The robotic system receives the message and responds with a WAYPOINT_LIST_READ message requesting the first waypoint item (seq==0).
 - a. A timeout must be started for the robotic system to wait on the WAYPOINT_LIST_ITEM (see section 4.2.1.3) response from the gRCS.
 - b. If the timeout expires without a response being received, then the WAYPOINT_LIST_READ message must be resent.
3. The gRCS receives WAYPOINT_LIST_READ message and responds with the requested waypoint item in a WAYPOINT_LIST_ITEM message.
4. The robotic system and the gRCS repeat this WAYPOINT_LIST_READ / WAYPOINT_LIST_ITEM cycle, iterating seq until all items are uploaded (seq==count-1).
5. After receiving the last waypoint item, the robotic system responds with WAYPOINT_LIST_ACK message (see section 4.2.1.4) with the type of WAYPOINT_LIST_ACCEPTED (see section 4.2.2.3) indicating that the waypoint list upload was completed successfully.
 - a. The robotic system should set the new data received to be the current waypoint list, discarding the original data.
 - b. The robotic system considers the upload complete.
6. The gRCS receives WAYPOINT_LIST_ACK message containing WAYPOINT_LIST_ACCEPTED to indicate the operation is complete.

Note:

- A timeout is set for every message that requires a response. If the timeout expires without a response being received, then the request must be resent.
- Waypoint items must be received in order. If an item is received out-of-sequence, the expected item should be re-requested by the robotic system (the out-of-sequence item is dropped).
- An error can be signaled in response to any request using a WAYPOINT_LIST_ACK message containing an error code. This must cancel the operation and restore the waypoint list to its previous state. For example, the robotic system might respond to the WAYPOINT_LIST_COUNT request with a WAYPOINT_LIST_NO_SPACE if there is not enough space to upload the waypoint list.
- Uploading an empty waypoint list (WAYPOINT_LIST_COUNT is 0) has the effect of clearing the current waypoint list.

4.1.2 Download the waypoint list from the robotic system

During the execution of the mission, it may be the case that the robotic system does a re-planning of the waypoint list (for example, when an obstacle is encountered along the way). If this occurs, the gRCS has to request the modified waypoint list from the robotic system.

The diagram below shows the communication sequence to download the current waypoint list from the robotic system (assuming all operations succeed).

Figure 97. Download the waypoint list from the robotic system

The sequence is like that for uploading the waypoint list. The main difference is that the gRCS sends `WAYPOINT_LIST_REQUEST` message (see section 4.2.1.5), which triggers the robotic system to respond with the current count of items. This starts a cycle where the gRCS requests waypoint items, and the robotic system supplies them.

Note:

- A timeout is set for every message that requires a response. If the timeout expires without a response being received, then the request must be resent.
- Waypoint items must be received in order. If an item is received out-of-sequence, the expected item should be re-requested by the gRCS (the out-of-sequence item is dropped).
- An error can be signaled in response to any request using a `WAYPOINT_LIST_ACK` message containing an error code. This must cancel the operation.

4.1.3 Download the checklist from the robotic system

Before starting the mission, the gRCS operator has to perform a set of checks associated with the robotic system. To do this, the gRCS must have previously asked the robotic system for its checklist.

The diagram below shows the communication sequence to download the checklist from the robotic system (assuming all operations succeed).

Figure 98. Download the checklist from the robotic system

In more detail, the sequence of operations is:

1. The gRCS sends a CHECK_LIST_REQUEST message (see section 4.2.1.6) requesting the robotic system checklist.
 - a. A timeout must be started for the gRCS to wait on the CHECK_LIST_COUNT (see section 4.2.1.7) response from the robotic system.
 - b. If the timeout expires without a response being received, then the CHECK_LIST_REQUEST message must be resent.

2. The robotic system receives message and responds with CHECK_LIST_COUNT message including the number of check items to be downloaded (count).
3. The gRCS receives the message and responds with a CHECK_LIST_READ message (see section 4.2.1.8) requesting the first check item (seq==0).
 - a. A timeout must be started for the gRCS to wait on the CHECK_LIST_ITEM (see section 4.2.1.9) response from the robotic system.
 - b. If the timeout expires without a response being received, then the CHECK_LIST_READ message must be resent.
4. The robotic system receives the CHECK_LIST_READ message and responds with the requested check item in a CHECK_LIST_ITEM message.
5. The gRCS and the robotic system repeat the CHECK_LIST_READ / CHECK_LIST_ITEM cycle, iterating seq until all items are downloaded (seq==count-1).
6. After receiving the last check item, the gRCS responds with a CHECK_LIST_ACK message (see section 4.2.1.10) with the type of CHECK_LIST_ACCEPTED (see section 4.2.2.4) indicating that the checklist download was completed successfully.
 - a. The gRCS should save the checklist received, discarding any lists it had previously.
 - b. The gRCS considers the download complete.
7. The robotic system receives the CHECK_LIST_ACK message containing CHECK_LIST_ACCEPTED to indicate the operation is complete.

Note:

- A timeout is set for every message that requires a response. If the timeout expires without a response being received, then the request must be resent.
- Check items must be received in order. If an item is received out-of-sequence, the expected item should be re-requested by the gRCS (the out-of-sequence item is dropped).
- An error can be signaled in response to any request using a CHECK_LIST_ACK message containing an error code. This must cancel the operation and restore the checklist inside of the gRCS to its previous state.
- Downloading an empty checklist (CHECK_LIST_COUNT is 0) has the effect of clearing the current checklist saved inside of the gRCS.

4.1.4 Download the list of alarms from the robotic system

During the execution of the mission, the gRCS can show the operator the status of a set of alarms predefined by the robotic system (for example, the status of its batteries). To do this, the gRCS must have previously requested the robotic system for its alarm list.

The diagram below shows the communication sequence to download the list of alarms from the robotic system (assuming all operations succeed).

Figure 99. Download the list of alarms from the robotic system

In more detail, the sequence of operations is:

1. The gRCS sends an `ALARM_LIST_REQUEST` message (see section 4.2.1.11) requesting the robotic system alarm list.
 - a. A timeout must be started for the gRCS to wait on the `ALARM_LIST_COUNT` (see section 4.2.1.12) response from the robotic system.
 - b. If the timeout expires without a response being received, then the `ALARM_LIST_REQUEST` message must be resent.

2. The robotic system receives message and responds with an `ALARM_LIST_COUNT` message including the number of alarm items to be downloaded (count).
3. The gRCS receives the message and responds with an `ALARM_LIST_READ` message (see section 4.2.1.13) requesting the first alarm item (seq==0).
 - a. A timeout must be started for the gRCS to wait on the `ALARM_LIST_ITEM` (see section 4.2.1.14) response from the robotic system.
 - b. If the timeout expires without a response being received, then the `ALARM_LIST_READ` message must be resent.
4. The robotic system receives the `ALARM_LIST_READ` message and responds with the requested alarm item in an `ALARM_LIST_ITEM` message.
5. The gRCS and robotic system repeat the `ALARM_LIST_READ` / `ALARM_LIST_ITEM` cycle, iterating seq until all items are downloaded (seq==count-1).
6. After receiving the last alarm item, the gRCS responds with an `ALARM_LIST_ACK` message (see section 4.2.1.15) with the type `ALARM_LIST_ACCEPTED` (see section 4.2.2.5) indicating that the download of the alarm list was completed successfully.
 - a. The gRCS should save the alarm list received, discarding any lists it had previously.
 - b. The gRCS considers the download complete.
7. The robotic system receives the `ALARM_LIST_ACK` message containing `ALARM_LIST_ACCEPTED` to indicate the operation is complete.

Note:

- A timeout is set for every message that requires a response. If the timeout expires without a response being received, then the request must be resent.
- Alarm items must be received in order. If an item is received out-of-sequence, the expected item should be re-requested by the gRCS (the out-of-sequence item is dropped).
- An error can be signaled in response to any request using an `ALARM_LIST_ACK` message containing an error code. This must cancel the operation and restore the alarm list inside of the gRCS to its previous state.
- Downloading an empty alarm list (`ALARM_LIST_COUNT` is 0) has the effect of clearing the current alarm list saved inside of the gRCS.

4.1.5 Download the list of high-level actions from the robotic system

During the execution of the mission, the gRCS operator can command the robotic system a set of high-level actions. To do this, the gRCS must have previously asked the robotic system for its high-level action list.

The diagram below shows the communication sequence to download the list of high-level actions from the robotic system (assuming all operations succeed).

Figure 100. Download the list of high-level actions from the robotic system

In more detail, the sequence of operations is:

1. The gRCS sends a `HL_ACTION_LIST_REQUEST` message (see section 4.2.1.16) requesting the robotic system high-level action list.
 - a. A timeout must be started for the gRCS to wait on the `HL_ACTION_LIST_COUNT` (see section 4.2.1.17) response from the robotic system.
 - b. If the timeout expires without a response being received, then the `HL_ACTION_LIST_REQUEST` message must be resent.

2. The robotic system receives message and responds with a HL_ACTION_LIST_COUNT message including the number of high-level action items to be downloaded (count).
3. The gRCS receives the message and responds with a HL_ACTION_LIST_READ message (see section 4.2.1.18) requesting the first high-level action item (seq==0).
 - a. A timeout must be started for the gRCS to wait on the HL_ACTION_LIST_ITEM (see section 4.2.1.19) response from the robotic system.
 - b. If the timeout expires without a response being received, then the HL_ACTION_LIST_READ message must be resent.
4. The robotic system receives the HL_ACTION_LIST_READ message and responds with the requested high-level action item in a HL_ACTION_LIST_ITEM message.
5. The gRCS and robotic system repeat the HL_ACTION_LIST_READ / HL_ACTION_LIST_ITEM cycle, iterating seq until all items are downloaded (seq==count-1).
6. After receiving the last high-level action item, the gRCS responds with an HL_ACTION_LIST_ACK message (see section 4.2.1.20) with the type HL_ACTION_LIST_ACCEPTED (see section 4.2.2.6) indicating that the download of the high-level action list was completed successfully.
 - a. The gRCS should save the high-level action list received, discarding any lists it had previously.
 - b. The gRCS considers the download complete.
7. The robotic system receives the HL_ACTION_LIST_ACK message containing HL_ACTION_LIST_ACCEPTED to indicate the operation is complete.

Note:

- A timeout is set for every message that requires a response. If the timeout expires without a response being received, then the request must be resent.
- High-level action items must be received in order. If an item is received out-of-sequence the expected item should be re-requested by the gRCS (the out-of-sequence item is dropped).
- An error can be signaled in response to any request using an HL_ACTION_LIST_ACK message containing an error code. This must cancel the operation and restore the high-level action list inside of the gRCS to its previous state.

- Downloading an empty high-level action list (HL_ACTION_LIST_COUNT is 0) has the effect of clearing the current high-level action list saved inside of the gRCS.

4.1.6 Send commands to the robotic system

During the execution of the mission, the gRCS operator can send commands to the robotic system (for example, the commands associated with high-level actions).

The diagram below shows the communication sequence to send a command to the robotic system.

Figure 101. Send commands to the robotic system

In more detail, the sequence of operations is:

1. The gRCS sends a COMMAND_LONG (see section 4.2.1.21) that includes the identifier of the command to be executed by the robotic system.
 - a. A timeout must be started for the gRCS to wait on the COMMAND_ACK (see section 4.2.1.22) response from the robotic system.
 - b. If the timeout expires without a response being received, then the COMMAND_LONG message must be resent, increasing the value of the confirmation field.
2. The robotic system receives the message and responds with a COMMAND_ACK with the type of MAV_RESULT_ACCEPTED (see section 4.2.2.2) indicating the command is valid.
 - a. The robotic system should execute the command.

- The gRCS receives the `COMMAND_ACK` containing `MAV_RESULT_ACCEPTED` to indicate the operation is complete.

Note:

- A timeout is set for every message that requires a response. If the timeout expires without a response being received, then the request must be resent.
- An error can be signaled in response to any request using a `COMMAND_ACK` message containing an error code. This must cancel the operation. For example, the robotic system might respond to the `COMMAND_LONG` request with a `MAV_RESULT_FAILED` if the command is valid, but the execution has failed.

4.1.7 Receive pose from the robotic system

During the execution of the mission, the robotic system periodically sends its position and orientation to the gRCS. As well as the position and orientation of its sensors.

The diagram below shows the communication sequence to receive the position and the orientation from the robotic system.

Figure 102. Receive pose from the robotic system

In more detail, the sequence of operations is:

- The robotic system sends the `LOCAL_POSITION_NED` (see section 4.2.1.23) and `ATTITUDE_QUATERNION` (see section 4.2.1.24) messages that will contain the position and orientation of the robotic system at each instant of time.
- The gRCS receives these messages and processes them, without the need to send a confirmation of their receipt.
- This cycle is repeated periodically until the connection between the robotic system and the gRCS is closed.

4.1.8 Receive alarm status from the robotic system

During the execution of the mission, the robotic system periodically sends to the gRCS the status of the alarms it has defined.

The diagram below shows the communication sequence to receive the alarm status from the robotic system.

Figure 103. Receive alarm status from the robotic system

In more detail, the sequence of operations is:

1. The robotic system sends an ALARM_STATUS message (see section 4.2.1.25) for each alarm that it has defined, differentiating them through their identifier.
 - a. This message will contain the state of the alarm specified at each instant of time (see section 4.2.2.7).
2. The gRCS receives these messages and processes them, without the need to send a confirmation of their receipt.
3. This cycle is repeated periodically until the connection between the robotic system and the gRCS is closed.

Note:

- The robotic system can send an ALARM_STATUS message at any time without having to wait for the next send cycle to start. So, if an error appears in any of the defined alarms, it can be reported to the gRCS immediately.

4.1.9 Receive message status from the robotic system

During the execution of the mission, the robotic system can send descriptive messages to the gRCS of events that have occurred.

The diagram below shows the communication sequence to receive a message status from the robotic system.

Figure 104. Receive message status from the robotic system

In more detail, the sequence of operations is:

1. When the robotic system detects an important event that may be of interest to the gRCS operator, it sends a TEXT_STATUS message (see section 4.2.1.26) containing a brief description of the event that has occurred.
 - a. These events contain an identifier to indicate the severity of the event that has occurred (see section 4.2.2.8), either to indicate that it is a warning or an error, or it is simply an informational event for the operator.
2. The gRCS receives this message and processes it, without the need to send a confirmation of its receipt.

4.1.10 Set current waypoint item to the robotic system

Once the robotic system has received the waypoint list and the mission has started, the gRCS can command the robotic system a specific waypoint item to perform.

The diagram below shows the communication sequence to set the current waypoint item to the robotic system. This diagram assumes that all operations are performed successfully.

Figure 105. Set current waypoint item to the robotic system

In more detail, the sequence of operations is:

1. The gRCS sends WAYPOINT_LIST_SET_CURRENT_ITEM message (see section 4.2.1.27), specifying the new sequence number (seq).
 - a. There is no specific timeout on the WAYPOINT_LIST_SET_CURRENT_ITEM message
2. The robotic system receives message and attempts to update the current waypoint sequence number.
 - a. On success, the robotic system must broadcast a WAYPOINT_LIST_CURRENT_ITEM message (see section 4.2.1.28) containing the current sequence number (seq).
 - b. On failure, the robotic system must broadcast a TEXT_STATUS stating the problem.

4.1.11 Receive waypoint list progress from the robotic system

During the execution of the mission, the robotic system sends messages with the progress of the waypoint list.

The diagram below shows the communication sequence to receive the waypoint list progress from the robotic system.

Figure 106. Receive waypoint list progress from the robotic system

In more detail, the sequence of operations is:

1. The robotic system must send a WAYPOINT_LIST_ITEM_REACHED message (see section 0) whenever a new waypoint item is reached. The message contains the seq number of the waypoint item reached.

2. The robotic system must also send a WAYPOINT_LIST_CURRENT_ITEM message if the current waypoint item is changed.
3. The gRCS receives these messages and processes them, without the need to send a confirmation of their receipt.

4.1.12 Heartbeat protocol

The heartbeat protocol is used to advertise the existence of a system on the MAVLink network.

Systems must regularly send a HEARTBEAT (see section 0) message and monitor for heartbeats from other systems.

The heartbeat allows other components to discover systems that are connected to the network and infer when they have disconnected. A component is considered to be connected to the network if its HEARTBEAT message is regularly received, and disconnected if a number of expected messages are not received.

Figure 107. Heartbeat protocol

4.2 Data model

The content and format of the messages exchanged between the robotic systems and the general robot control station are defined below.

4.2.1 Messages

MAVLink messages are encapsulated in a packet in the following format.

- **Packet start marker:** Protocol-specific start-of-text (STX) marker used to indicate the beginning of a new packet. Any system that does not understand protocol version will skip the packet.
- **Payload length:** Indicates length of the following PAYLOAD section (fixed for a particular message).
- **Incompatibility Flags:** Flags that are used to indicate features that a MAVLink library must support in order to handle the package.
- **Compatibility Flags:** Flags that are used to indicate the features that will not prevent a MAVLink library from handling the package.
- **Packet sequence number:** Used to detect packet loss. Components increment value for each message sent.
- **System ID:** Identifier of system (e.g. robotic system) sending the message. Used to differentiate systems on network.
- **Component ID:** Identifier of component sending the message. Used to differentiate components in a system (e.g. autopilot and a camera).
- **Message ID:** Identifier of message type in payload. Used to decode data back into message object.
- **Payload data:** Message data. Content depends on message type.
- **Checksum:** CRC-16/MCRF4XX for message (excluding magic byte), used to allow detection of message corruption.
- **Signature:** (Optional) Signature to ensure that messages originate from a trusted source.

The following table shows the reserved system identifiers (**System ID**) for each partner.

Table 3. Reserved system identifiers per partner

Partner	System IDs
CATEC	From 30 to 49
ETHZ	From 50 to 69
GEIR	From 70 to 89
RBNK	From 90 to 109
SINTEF	From 110 to 129
USE	From 130 to 149

Regarding the component identifier (**Component ID**), the desired value can be freely used for each component of the system (that is, for each sensor used in the system). Except for the robotic vehicle, which must be identified with the value “0”.

The messages used at the interface between the gRCS and the robotic system are described below.

4.2.1.1 WAYPOINT_LIST_COUNT

Send the number of items in the waypoint list. This is used to initiate a waypoint list upload or as a response to a WAYPOINT_LIST_REQUEST message when downloading the waypoint list.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
count	uint16_t	Number of waypoint items in the sequence

4.2.1.2 WAYPOINT_LIST_READ

Request waypoint item data for a specific sequence number be sent by the recipient using a WAYPOINT_LIST_ITEM message. Used for waypoint list upload and download.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
seq	uint16_t	Waypoint ID (sequence number). Starts at zero

4.2.1.3 WAYPOINT_LIST_ITEM

Message encoding a waypoint item. Used for waypoint list upload and download.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID

task_id	uint32_t	Identifier of the associated inspection task
seq	uint16_t	Waypoint ID (sequence number). Starts at zero. Increases monotonically for each waypoint, no gaps in the sequence (0,1,2,3,4)
command	uint16_t	The scheduled action for the waypoint (see MAV_CMD enum)
autocontinue	uint8_t	Autocontinue to next waypoint
param1	float	PARAM1 (see MAV_CMD enum)
param2	float	PARAM2 (see MAV_CMD enum)
param3	float	PARAM3 (see MAV_CMD enum)
param4	float	PARAM4 (see MAV_CMD enum)
x	float	PARAM5: x position in meters
y	float	PARAM6: y position in meters
z	float	PARAM7: z position in meters

4.2.1.4 WAYPOINT_LIST_ACK

Acknowledgement message when a system completes a waypoint list operation (e.g. sent by robotic system after it has uploaded all waypoint items). The message includes a WAYPOINT_LIST_RESULT indicating either success or the type of failure.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
type	uint8_t	Waypoint list operation result (see WAYPOINT_LIST_RESULT enum)

4.2.1.5 WAYPOINT_LIST_REQUEST

Initiate the waypoint list download operation from a system.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID

4.2.1.6 CHECK_LIST_REQUEST

Initiate the checklist download operation from a system.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID

4.2.1.7 CHECK_LIST_COUNT

Send the number of items in a checklist. This is used as a response to a CHECK_LIST_REQUEST message when downloading the checklist.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
count	uint16_t	Number of check items in the sequence

4.2.1.8 CHECK_LIST_READ

Request check item value for a specific sequence number be sent by the recipient using a CHECK_LIST_ITEM message. Used for checklist download.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
index	uint16_t	Check index. Starts at zero

4.2.1.9 CHECK_LIST_ITEM

The value of a check item. This is used as a response to CHECK_LIST_READ when downloading the checklist.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
index	uint16_t	Check index. Starts at zero
name	char[20]	Check name string
description	char[231]	Check description string

4.2.1.10 CHECK_LIST_ACK

Acknowledgment message when a system completes the checklist download operation. The message includes a CHECK_LIST_RESULT indicating either success or the type of failure.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
type	uint8_t	Checklist operation result (see CHECK_LIST_RESULT enum)

4.2.1.11 ALARM_LIST_REQUEST

Initiate the alarm list download operation from a system.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID

4.2.1.12 ALARM_LIST_COUNT

Send the number of items in an alarm list. This is used as a response to an ALARM_LIST_REQUEST message when downloading the alarm list.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
count	uint16_t	Number of alarm items in the sequence

4.2.1.13 ALARM_LIST_READ

Request alarm item value for a specific sequence number be sent by the recipient using an ALARM_LIST_ITEM message. Used for alarm list download.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
index	uint16_t	Alarm index. Starts at zero

4.2.1.14 ALARM_LIST_ITEM

The value of an alarm item. This is used as a response to an ALARM_LIST_READ message when downloading the alarm list.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
index	uint16_t	Alarm index. Starts at zero
name	char[20]	Alarm name string
description	char[231]	Alarm description string

4.2.1.15 ALARM_LIST_ACK

Acknowledgment message when a system completes the alarm list download operation. The message includes an ALARM_LIST_RESULT indicating either success or the type of failure.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
type	uint8_t	Alarm list operation result (see ALARM_LIST_RESULT enum)

4.2.1.16 HL_ACTION_LIST_REQUEST

Initiate the high-level action list download operation from a system.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID

4.2.1.17 HL_ACTION_LIST_COUNT

Send the number of items in a high-level action list. This is used as a response to a HL_ACTION_LIST_REQUEST message when downloading the high-level action list.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
count	uint16_t	Number of high-level action items in the sequence

4.2.1.18 HL_ACTION_LIST_READ

Request high-level action item value for a specific sequence number be sent by the recipient using an HL_ACTION_LIST_ITEM message. Used for high-level action list download.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
index	uint16_t	High-level action index. Starts at zero

4.2.1.19 HL_ACTION_LIST_ITEM

The value of a high-level action item. This is used as a response to an HL_ACTION_LIST_READ message when downloading the high-level action list.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
index	uint16_t	High-level action index. Starts at zero
command	uint16_t	Command ID of the command associated with the high-level action (see MAV_CMD enum)
name	char[20]	High-level action name string
description	char[229]	High-level action description string

4.2.1.20 HL_ACTION_LIST_ACK

Acknowledgment message when a system completes the high-level action list download operation. The message includes a HL_ACTION_LIST_RESULT indicating either success or the type of failure.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
type	uint8_t	High-level action list operation result (see HL_ACTION_LIST_RESULT enum)

4.2.1.21 *COMMAND_LONG*

Message to encode a command to be sent to a specific system. The message encodes commands into up to 7 float parameters.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
command	uint16_t	Command ID of command to send (see MAV_CMD enum)
confirmation	uint8_t	Number of resends: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0: First transmission • 1-255: Confirmation transmissions
param1	float	Parameter 1 for the specific command
param2	float	Parameter 2 for the specific command
param3	float	Parameter 3 for the specific command
param4	float	Parameter 4 for the specific command
param5	float	Parameter 5 for the specific command
param6	float	Parameter 6 for the specific command
param7	float	Parameter 7 for the specific command

4.2.1.22 *COMMAND_ACK*

Command acknowledgement. Includes result (success, failure, still in progress) and may include progress information and additional detail about failure reasons.

Report status of a command. Includes feedback whether the command was executed.

Field Name	Type	Description
command	uint16_t	Command ID of acknowledged command (see MAV_CMD enum)
result	uint8_t	Result of command (see MAV_RESULT enum)

4.2.1.23 LOCAL_POSITION_NED

The local position of a specific system. Coordinate frame is right-handed, Z-axis down (aeronautical frame, NED convention).

Field Name	Type	Description
time_boot_ms	uint32_t	Timestamp (time since system boot), in milliseconds
x	float	X Position, in meters
y	float	Y Position, in meters
z	float	Z Position, in meters
vx	float	X Speed, in meters/seconds
vy	float	Y Speed, in meters/seconds
vz	float	Z Speed, in meters/seconds

4.2.1.24 ATTITUDE_QUATERNION

The attitude in the aeronautical frame (right-handed, Z-down, X-front, Y-right), expressed as quaternion. Quaternion order is w, x, y, z and a zero rotation would be expressed as (1 0 0 0).

Field Name	Type	Description
time_boot_ms	uint32_t	Timestamp (time since system boot), in milliseconds
q1	float	Quaternion component 1, w (1 in null-rotation)
q2	float	Quaternion component 2, x (0 in null-rotation)
q3	float	Quaternion component 3, y (0 in null-rotation)
q4	float	Quaternion component 4, z (0 in null-rotation)
rollspeed	float	Roll angular speed, in radians/seconds
pitchspeed	float	Pitch angular speed, in radians/seconds
yawspeed	float	Yaw angular speed, in radians/seconds

4.2.1.25 ALARM_STATUS

This message is used to inform the gRCS of the robotic system's alarm status (indicated by its index).

Field Name	Type	Description
time_boot_ms	uint32_t	Timestamp (time since system boot), in milliseconds
index	uint16_t	Alarm index
status	uint8_t	Alarm status (see ALARM_STATUS_FLAGS enum)
errors_count	uint16_t	Alarm errors count since system boot
warns_count	uint16_t	Alarm warnings count since system boot

4.2.1.26 TEXT_STATUS

This message is used to inform the gRCS of any type of warning or error that occurred in the robotic system. It can even be used to send information messages to the gRCS.

Field Name	Type	Description
severity	uint8_t	Severity of status (see TEXT_STATUS_FLAGS enum)
text	char[254]	Status text message, without null termination character

4.2.1.27 WAYPOINT_LIST_SET_CURRENT_ITEM

Set the waypoint item with sequence number seq as current item.

Field Name	Type	Description
target_system	uint8_t	System ID
target_component	uint8_t	Component ID
seq	uint16_t	Waypoint ID (sequence number). Starts at zero

4.2.1.28 WAYPOINT_LIST_CURRENT_ITEM

Message that announces the sequence number of the current active waypoint item. The robotic system will move towards this item of the waypoint list.

Field Name	Type	Description
seq	uint16_t	Waypoint ID (sequence number). Starts at zero

4.2.1.29 WAYPOINT_LIST_ITEM_REACHED

Message that announces that a certain item of the waypoint list has been reached.

Field Name	Type	Description
seq	uint16_t	Waypoint ID (sequence number). Starts at zero

4.2.1.30 HEARTBEAT

The heartbeat message shows that a system is present and responding.

Field Name	Type	Description
type	uint8_t	Vehicle or component type
system_status	uint8_t	System status flag

4.2.2 Enumerations

4.2.2.1 MAV_CMD

Command identifier used in WAYPOINT_LIST_ITEM and COMMAND_LONG messages. For each command identifier, the values of up to 7 parameters that are packaged within messages are defined.

- MAV_CMD_NAV_WAYPOINT_QUATERNION

Navigate to waypoint.

Param	Label Name	Description
1	Quaternion W	Quaternion component w (1 in null-rotation)
2	Quaternion X	Quaternion component x (0 in null-rotation)
3	Quaternion Y	Quaternion component y (0 in null-rotation)
4	Quaternion Z	Quaternion component z (0 in null-rotation)

5	Position X	Position component x, in meters
6	Position Y	Position component y, in meters
7	Position Z	Position component z, in meters

- MAV_CMD_NAV_RETURN_TO_LAUNCH

Return to launch location.

Param	Label Name	Description
1	Reserved	Reserved
2	Reserved	Reserved
3	Reserved	Reserved
4	Reserved	Reserved
5	Reserved	Reserved
6	Reserved	Reserved
7	Reserved	Reserved

- MAV_CMD_NAV_LAND_QUATERNION

Land at location.

Param	Label Name	Description
1	Quaternion W	Quaternion component w (1 in null-rotation)
2	Quaternion X	Quaternion component x (0 in null-rotation)
3	Quaternion Y	Quaternion component y (0 in null-rotation)
4	Quaternion Z	Quaternion component z (0 in null-rotation)
5	Position X	Position component x, in meters
6	Position Y	Position component y, in meters
7	Position Z	Position component z, in meters

- MAV_CMD_NAV_TAKEOFF_QUATERNION

Takeoff from ground / hand.

Param	Label Name	Description
1	Quaternion W	Quaternion component w (1 in null-rotation)
2	Quaternion X	Quaternion component x (0 in null-rotation)
3	Quaternion Y	Quaternion component y (0 in null-rotation)
4	Quaternion Z	Quaternion component z (0 in null-rotation)
5	Position X	Position component x, in meters
6	Position Y	Position component y, in meters
7	Position Z	Position component z, in meters

- MAV_CMD_DO_CHANGE_SPEED

Change speed and/or throttle set points.

Param	Label Name	Description
1	Speed Type	Speed type (0=Airspeed, 1=Ground Speed, 2=Climb Speed, 3=Descent Speed)
2	Speed	Speed, in m/s (-1 indicates no change)
3	Throttle	Throttle, in % (-1 indicates no change)
4	Relative	0: absolute, 1: relative
5	Reserved	Reserved
6	Reserved	Reserved
7	Reserved	Reserved

- MAV_CMD_DO_CHANGE_ALTITUDE

Change altitude set point.

Param	Label Name	Description
1	Altitude	Altitude, in meters
2	Reserved	Reserved
3	Reserved	Reserved
4	Reserved	Reserved
5	Reserved	Reserved
6	Reserved	Reserved
7	Reserved	Reserved

- MAV_CMD_DO_SET_HOME_QUATERNION

Changes the home location either to the current location or a specified location.

Param	Label Name	Description
1	Quaternion W	Quaternion component w (1 in null-rotation)
2	Quaternion X	Quaternion component x (0 in null-rotation)
3	Quaternion Y	Quaternion component y (0 in null-rotation)
4	Quaternion Z	Quaternion component z (0 in null-rotation)
5	Position X	Position component x, in meters
6	Position Y	Position component y, in meters
7	Position Z	Position component z, in meters

- MAV_CMD_DO_PAUSE_CONTINUE

Hold the current position or continue.

Param	Label Name	Description
1	Continue	0: Pause current mission or reposition command, hold current position. 1: Continue mission.
2	Reserved	Reserved

3	Reserved	Reserved
4	Reserved	Reserved
5	Reserved	Reserved
6	Reserved	Reserved
7	Reserved	Reserved

4.2.2.2 MAV_RESULT

Result of command operation (in a COMMAND_ACK message).

Value	Field Name	Description
0	MAV_RESULT_ACCEPTED	Command is valid (is supported and has valid parameters) and was executed.
1	MAV_RESULT_TEMPORARILY_REJECTED	Command is valid but cannot be executed at this time. This is used to indicate a problem that should be fixed just by waiting (e.g. a state machine is busy, cannot arm because has not got GPS lock, etc.). Retrying later should work.
2	MAV_RESULT_DENIED	Command is invalid (is supported but has invalid parameters). Retrying the same command and parameters will not work.
3	MAV_RESULT_UNSUPPORTED	Command is not supported (unknown).
4	MAV_RESULT_FAILED	Command is valid, but execution has failed. This is used to indicate any non-temporary or unexpected problem, i.e. any problem that must be fixed before the command can succeed/be retried. For example, attempting to write a file when out of memory, attempting to arm when sensors are not calibrated, etc.
5	MAV_RESULT_IN_PROGRESS	Command is valid and is being executed. This will be followed by further progress updates, i.e. the component may send further COMMAND_ACK messages with result MAV_RESULT_IN_PROGRESS (at a rate decided by the implementation), and must terminate by sending a COMMAND_ACK message with final result of the operation. The progress field of COMMAND_ACK message can be used to indicate the progress of the operation.

6	MAV_RESULT_CANCELLED	Command has been cancelled (as a result of receiving a COMMAND_CANCEL message).
---	----------------------	---

4.2.2.3 WAYPOINT_LIST_RESULT

Result of a waypoint list operation (in a WAYPOINT_LIST_ACK message).

Value	Field Name	Description
0	WAYPOINT_LIST_ACCEPTED	Waypoint list accepted OK.
1	WAYPOINT_LIST_ERROR	Generic error.
2	WAYPOINT_LIST_UNSUPPORTED	Command is not supported.
3	WAYPOINT_LIST_NO_SPACE	Waypoint items exceed storage space.
4	WAYPOINT_LIST_INVALID	One of the parameters has an invalid value.
5	WAYPOINT_LIST_INVALID_PARAM1	Param1 has an invalid value.
6	WAYPOINT_LIST_INVALID_PARAM2	Param2 has an invalid value.
7	WAYPOINT_LIST_INVALID_PARAM3	Param3 has an invalid value.
8	WAYPOINT_LIST_INVALID_PARAM4	Param4 has an invalid value.
9	WAYPOINT_LIST_INVALID_PARAM5	Param5 (x) has an invalid value.
10	WAYPOINT_LIST_INVALID_PARAM6	Param6 (y) has an invalid value.
11	WAYPOINT_LIST_INVALID_PARAM7	Param7 (z) has an invalid value.
12	WAYPOINT_LIST_INVALID_SEQUENCE	Waypoint item received out of sequence.

13	WAYPOINT_LIST_CANCELLED	Current waypoint list operation cancelled (waypoint list upload or download).
----	-------------------------	---

4.2.2.4 CHECK_LIST_RESULT

Result of checklist downloading operation (in a CHECK_LIST_ACK message).

Value	Field Name	Description
0	CHECK_LIST_ACCEPTED	Checklist accepted OK.
1	CHECK_LIST_ERROR	Generic error.
2	CHECK_LIST_NO_SPACE	Checklist items exceed storage space.
3	CHECK_LIST_INVALID_SEQUENCE	Checklist item received out of sequence.
4	CHECK_LIST_CANCELLED	Current checklist download operation cancelled.

4.2.2.5 ALARM_LIST_RESULT

Result of alarm list downloading operation (in an ALARM_LIST_ACK message).

Value	Field Name	Description
0	ALARM_LIST_ACCEPTED	Alarm list accepted OK.
1	ALARM_LIST_ERROR	Generic error.
2	ALARM_LIST_NO_SPACE	Alarm list items exceed storage space.
3	ALARM_LIST_INVALID_SEQUENCE	Alarm list item received out of sequence.
4	ALARM_LIST_CANCELLED	Current alarm list download operation cancelled.

4.2.2.6 HL_ACTION_LIST_RESULT

Result of high-level action list downloading operation (in an HL_ACTION_LIST_ACK message).

Value	Field Name	Description
0	HL_ACTION_LIST_ACCEPTED	High-level action list accepted OK.
1	HL_ACTION_LIST_ERROR	Generic error.
2	HL_ACTION_LIST_NO_SPACE	High-level action list items exceed storage space.
3	HL_ACTION_LIST_INVALID_SEQUENCE	High-level action list item received out of sequence.
4	HL_ACTION_LIST_CANCELLED	Current high-level action list download operation cancelled.

4.2.2.7 ALARM_STATUS_FLAGS

Alarm status flags used in ALARM_STATUS messages.

Value	Field Name	Description
0	ALARM_STATUS_OK	Alarm in ok status
1	ALARM_STATUS_WARNING	Alarm in warning status
2	ALARM_STATUS_ERROR	Alarm in error status

4.2.2.8 TEXT_STATUS_FLAGS

Indicates the severity level, used for TEXT_STATUS messages to indicate their relative urgency.

Value	Field Name	Description
0	TEXT_STATUS_ERROR	Indicates an error in systems.
1	TEXT_STATUS_WARNING	Indicates about a possible future error if this is not resolved within a given timeframe. Example would be a low battery warning.

2	TEXT_STATUS_INFO	Normal operational messages. Useful for logging. No action is required for these messages.
---	------------------	--

5. Communications interface with DDHL

This section defines the communication interface of the Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer and the gRCS. The communication is based upon RESTful interfaces, with DDHL being the passive component, meaning that any data exchange attempt is initiated by the gRCS.

5.1 Communication sequences

5.1.1 Get mission initiation data

For a mission to be initiated, the gRCS has to request the inspection plan data from the Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer providing the relevant inspection plan identifier. Once the data is received by the DDHL, it will forward the request to the DMS and route the DMS's response back to the gRCS.

Figure 108. Mission Initiation: Get Inspection Plan data

Considering the size and complexity of the data necessary to start a mission, this communication sequence can be implemented either as a whole (as depicted in the image above) or in parts, where a single request is made for each data field.

Figure 109, Figure 110 and Figure 111 showcase the aforementioned scenario for the inspection tasks, assets and notes.

Figure 109. Mission Initiation: Get Inspection Task

Figure 110. Mission Initiation: Asset field

Figure 111. Mission Initiation: Notes field

5.1.2 Send mission results

This sequence describes the actions performed by the gRCS and DDHL in order to exchange the mission result data. This data, for example, is the filled post-mission checklist, any alarms produced or the trajectory the robotic system followed during the mission. Upon receiving the request, the DDHL shall transform, augment and forward the received data to the DMS to reach its permanent storage location case.

Figure 112. Mission result data exchange

Similarly to the mission initiation process, the relevant data can be exchanged in a single or multiple messages. Figure 113, Figure 114, Figure 115 and Figure 116 present the mission result data exchange communication sequence in the single messages.

Figure 113. Mission result: Mission task data

Figure 114. Mission result: Notes

Figure 115. Mission result: Planned trajectory

Figure 116. Mission result: Path followed

5.2 Data model

For the ease of communication between gRCS and DDHL, it has been agreed that the link between the two parties shall be implemented via a REST API. Apart from that, the message body will be of JSON type, thus allowing for flexibility and readability. The content and format of the messages exchanged between the robotic systems and the general robot control station are defined below using OpenAPI version 3.0.1.

5.2.1 Mission Initiation

For a mission to initiate, all available information for the corresponding inspection plan and inspection tasks shall be forwarded to the gRCS. The message (or messages) exchanged during this stage is the following.

```
inspectionPlan:
  type: object
  properties:
    id:
      type: string
    name:
      type: string
    description:
      type: string
    creationDatetime:
      type: string
    updateDatetime:
      type: string
    properties:
      type: string
    fileMeta:
      type: array
      items:
        $ref: '#/components/schemas/fileMeta'
    asset:
      $ref: '#/components/schemas/asset'
    inspectionTasks:
      type: array
      items:
        $ref: '#/components/schemas/inspectionTask'
    missionIds:
      type: array
      items:
        type: string
```

```
inspectionTask:
  type: object
  properties:
    id:
      type: string
    name:
      type: string
    description:
      type: string
    creationDatetime:
      type: string
    updateDatetime:
      type: string
    properties:
      type: string
    missionTask:
      type: string
  type:
    $ref: '#/components/schemas/inspectionType'
  personnel:
    type: array
    items:
      $ref: '#/components/schemas/personnel'
  robotic:
    type: array
    items:
      $ref: '#/components/schemas/robotic'
  fileMeta:
    type: array
    items:
      $ref: '#/components/schemas/fileMeta'
```

```
inspectionType:
  type: object
  properties:
    id:
      type: string
    name:
      type: string
    description:
      type: string
    creationDatetime:
      type: string
    updateDatetime:
      type: string
    properties:
      type: string
```

```
personnel:  
  type: object  
  properties:  
    id:  
      type: string  
    name:  
      type: string  
    originalName:  
      type: string  
    role:  
      type: string  
    creationDatetime:  
      type: string  
    updateDatetime:  
      type: string  
    properties:  
      type: string
```

```
payload:  
  type: object  
  properties:  
    id:  
      type: string  
    serialNumber:  
      type: string  
    type:  
      type: string  
    description:  
      type: string  
    creationDatetime:  
      type: string  
    updateDatetime:  
      type: string  
    properties:  
      type: string
```

```
robotic:
  type: object
  properties:
    id:
      type: string
    name:
      type: string
    description:
      type: string
    creationDatetime:
      type: string
    updateDatetime:
      type: string
    properties:
      type: string
    payloads:
      type: array
      items:
        $ref: '#/components/schemas/payload'
```

```
fileMeta:
  type: object
  properties:
    url:
      type: string
    mimeType:
      type: string
    size:
      type: string
    originalName:
      type: string
    contentType:
      type: string
    creationDatetime:
      type: string
    updateDatetime:
      type: string
    properties:
      type: string
```

```
asset:
  type: object
  properties:
    id:
      type: string
    name:
      type: string
    description:
      type: string
    creationDatetime:
      type: string
    updateDatetime:
      type: string
    properties:
      type: string
    inspectionLoc:
      $ref: '#/components/schemas/inspectionLocation'
    fileMeta:
      type: array
      items:
        $ref: '#/components/schemas/fileMeta'
    measurements:
      type: object
```

```
inspectionLocation:
  type: object
  properties:
    id:
      type: string
    name:
      type: string
    description:
      type: string
    creationDatetime:
      type: string
    updateDatetime:
      type: string
    properties:
      type: string
    subType:
      type: string
```

Depending on the mission type and status, the messages shall contain all or a subset of the fields specified above.

5.2.2 Mission (task) Completion

Once a mission (or a mission task corresponding to a mission) is complete, the gRCS shall forward the data and logs generated by the robot to the DDHL in order to be transformed and forwarded to the DMS. The messages exchanged during this stage are the following.

```
mission:
  type: object
  properties:
    id:
      type: string
    name:
      type: string
    notes:
      type: string
    executionDatetime:
      type: string
    properties:
      type: string
    pathFollowed:
      $ref: '#/components/schemas/Feature'
    plannedTrajectory:
      $ref: '#/components/schemas/Feature'
    eventLog:
      type: string
    checkList:
      type: string
    missionTasks:
      type: array
      items:
        $ref: '#/components/schemas/missionTask'
```

```
missionTask:
  type: object
  properties:
    id:
      type: string
    name:
      type: string
    description:
      type: string
    notes:
      type: string
    executionDatetime:
      type: string
    properties:
      type: string
    filedata:
      type: array
      items:
        $ref: '#/components/schemas/fileMeta'
```

```
Feature:
  type: object
  description: GeoJSON Feature
  properties:
    id:
      type: object
    type:
      type: string
      enum:
        - Feature
    geometry:
      $ref: '#/components/schemas/Geometry'
    properties:
      type: object
      additionalProperties:
        type: object
  x-go-type:
    type: Feature
  import:
    package: github.com/paulmach/orb/geojson
```

```
FeatureCollection:
  type: object
  properties:
    features:
      type: array
      items:
        $ref: '#/components/schemas/Feature'
  x-go-type:
    type: FeatureCollection
  import:
    package: github.com/paulmach/orb/geojson
```

```
Geometry:
  type: object
  description: GeoJSON geometry
  discriminator:
    propertyName: type
  externalDocs:
    url: 'http://GeoJSON.org/GeoJSON-spec.html#geometry-objects'
  properties:
    dimensions:
      description: The number of dimensions
      type: integer
    type:
      $ref: '#/components/schemas/GeometryType'
  x-go-type:
    type: Geometry
  import:
    package: github.com/paulmach/orb/geojson
```

```
GeometryType:
  type: string
  enum:
    - Point
    - LineString
    - Polygon
    - MultiPoint
    - MultiLineString
    - MultiPolygon
  description: the geometry type
```

```
Point2D:  
  type: array  
  maxItems: 2  
  minItems: 2  
  items:  
    type: number
```

```
Point:  
  type: object  
  description: GeoJSON geometry  
  externalDocs:  
    url: 'http://GeoJSON.org/GeoJSON-spec.html#id2'  
  allOf:  
    - $ref: '#/components/schemas/Geometry'  
    - properties:  
        coordinates:  
          $ref: '#/components/schemas/Point2D'  
  x-go-type:  
    type: Point  
  import:  
    package: github.com/paulmach/orb/geojson  
  validate: false
```

```
LineString:  
  type: object  
  description: GeoJSON geometry  
  externalDocs:  
    url: 'http://GeoJSON.org/GeoJSON-spec.html#id3'  
  allOf:  
    - $ref: '#/components/schemas/Geometry'  
    - properties:  
        coordinates:  
          type: array  
          items:  
            $ref: '#/components/schemas/Point2D'  
  x-go-type:  
    type: LineString  
  import:  
    package: github.com/paulmach/orb/geojson
```

```
Polygon:
  type: object
  description: GeoJSON geometry
  externalDocs:
    url: 'http://GeoJSON.org/GeoJSON-spec.html#id4'
  allOf:
    - $ref: '#/components/schemas/Geometry'
    - properties:
        coordinates:
          type: array
          items:
            type: array
            items:
              $ref: '#/components/schemas/Point2D'
  x-go-type:
    type: Polygon
  import:
    package: github.com/paulmach/orb/geojson
```

```
MultiPoint:
  type: object
  description: GeoJSON geometry
  externalDocs:
    url: 'http://GeoJSON.org/GeoJSON-spec.html#id5'
  allOf:
    - $ref: '#/components/schemas/Geometry'
    - properties:
        coordinates:
          type: array
          items:
            $ref: '#/components/schemas/Point2D'
  x-go-type:
    type: MultiPoint
  import:
    package: github.com/paulmach/orb/geojson
```

```
MultiLineString:
  type: object
  description: GeoJSON geometry
  externalDocs:
    url: 'http://GeoJSON.org/GeoJSON-spec.html#id6'
  allOf:
    - $ref: '#/components/schemas/Geometry'
    - properties:
        coordinates:
          type: array
          items:
            type: array
            items:
              $ref: '#/components/schemas/Point2D'
  x-go-type:
    type: MultiLineString
  import:
    package: github.com/paulmach/orb/geojson
```

```
MultiPolygon:
  type: object
  description: GeoJSON geometry
  externalDocs:
    url: 'http://GeoJSON.org/GeoJSON-spec.html#id6'
  allOf:
    - $ref: '#/components/schemas/Geometry'
    - properties:
        coordinates:
          type: array
          items:
            type: array
            items:
              type: array
              items:
                $ref: '#/components/schemas/Point2D'
  x-go-type:
    type: MultiPolygon
  import:
    package: github.com/paulmach/orb/geojson
```

```
GeometryCollection:
  type: object
  description: GeoJSON geometry collection
  required:
    - type
    - geometries
  externalDocs:
    url: 'http://GeoJSON.org/GeoJSON-spec.html#geometrycollection'
  properties:
    type:
      type: string
      enum:
        - GeometryCollection
    geometries:
      type: array
      items:
        $ref: '#/components/schemas/Geometry'
  x-go-type:
    type: GeometryCollection
  import:
    package: github.com/paulmach/orb/geojson
```

As for the mission initiation messages, depending on the mission type and status, the messages shall contain all or a subset of the fields specified above.

6. Conclusions

In this document, the definition of the modules that make up the software architecture of the gRCS system has been expanded. In addition, the design of its graphical user interface has been presented, covering all the requirements defined in previous documentation. Finally, the communication interfaces with robotic systems and with the DDHL have been defined.

With all the above defined, the development of the gRCS system can be considered advanced enough to be able to start the next phase, which is the integration with the rest of the PILOTING system.